

Designing Chua's Circuit by Using DSpice Software

Dhiabi Fathi

Laboratory of Metallic and Semiconducting Materials (LMSM), Department of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Sciences and Technology, Biskra University, B.P. 145 RP, 07000 Biskra, Algeria

E-mail: f.dhiabi@univ-biskra.dz

Abstract:

The Chua circuit, renowned for its simplicity and rich dynamical behavior, serves as a fundamental example in the study of nonlinear circuits and chaos theory. This paper presents a comprehensive approach to designing a Chua circuit using DSpice (Desing and Simulation Circuit by Spice), a powerful simulation tool widely used in the field of electronics. The design process involves the selection and configuration of essential components such as resistors, capacitors, inductors, and the Chua diode. Detailed simulation results demonstrate the circuit's ability to exhibit chaotic behavior, highlighting key parameters and their impact on the system's dynamics. The SPICE simulation provides valuable insights into the circuit's performance, offering a practical framework for researchers and engineers to explore nonlinear dynamics in electronic circuits.

Keywords: DSpice, Circuits, CAD, oscillator , Chua's.

I. Introduction

The Chua circuit, first introduced by Leon Chua in 1983, is a cornerstone in the study of chaos theory within electronic systems. Characterized by its simplicity and ability to generate complex, chaotic behavior, the Chua circuit has become a popular subject of research and educational interest. The circuit's chaotic (Fig.1) nature stems from its nonlinear components, primarily the Chua diode, which introduces the necessary nonlinearity for chaos to emerge [1].

Fig. 1 (a). Chua's circuit. The component NR is a nonlinear negative resistance called a Chua's diode. (b) The current–voltage characteristic of the Chua diode

The differential equations governing the Chua circuit are:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dV_1}{dt} &= \frac{1}{C_1}(G(V_2 - V_1) - f(V_1)) \\ \frac{dV_2}{dt} &= \frac{1}{C_2}(G(V_1 - V_2) + I_L) \\ \frac{dI_L}{dt} &= \frac{1}{L}(-V_2 - R_L I_L) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The nonlinear function $f(V_1)$ is defined as:

$$f(V_1) = m_1 V_1 + \frac{m_0 - m_1}{2} (|V_1 + E| - |V_1 - E|) \quad (2)$$

Parameters

V_1 : Voltage across capacitor C_1
 V_2 : Voltage across capacitor C_2

G : Conductance.
 m_0, m_1 : Slopes of the nonlinear characteristic of the Chua diode.
 E : Breakpoint voltage of the Chua diode.

II. Simulating Chua's Using DSpice

DSpice [2][3] is a powerful tool for simulating electronic circuits, widely used in both academia and industry. To simulate the system of Chua's using DSpice, we need to create an equivalent electronic circuit that captures the behavior described by the differential equation.

Fig. 1 The interface graphic of DSpice

a. Circuit design

The Fig .2 is circuit for the Chua's, component explanation:

- **L1 (18mH)**: Inductor.
- **C1 (47nF)**: Capacitor.
- **C2 (7.6nF)**: Capacitor.
- **D1,D2(D1N4001)** : Diodes.
- **R1(1.6K)**: Resistor
- **R2,R2(3.3K)** : Resistor
- **R6,R7(290)** : Resistor
- **R8(1.2K)** : Resistor
- **OPAm(LM358/NS)**

Fig. 2 The circuit of Chua's

Result of simulation as shown in Fig. 3. [4].

Fig. 3 The result of simulation

III. Conclusion

Designing a Chua circuit using DSpice provides a practical and insightful approach to studying nonlinear dynamics and chaos theory. The process involves setting up the differential equations, creating an equivalent SPICE model, and conducting simulations to analyze the circuit's behavior. The simulation results highlight the circuit's ability to exhibit chaotic dynamics, making it an excellent tool for both educational and research purposes. By leveraging DSpice powerful simulation capabilities, researchers can explore various configurations and gain a deeper understanding of the principles underlying chaotic systems.

References

1. Matsumoto, T., Chua, L., & Komuro, M. (1985). The double scroll. *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems*, 32(8), 797-818. doi: [10.1109/TCS.1985.1085791](https://doi.org/10.1109/TCS.1985.1085791)
2. "The graphical user interface (GUI) of DSpice". <https://dspice.sourceforge.io/doc/>
3. Dhiabi, F. (2024). DSpice: New Software for Modeling Analog Elements and Circuit Simulation Using SPICE. doi: [10.5281/zenodo.11219972](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11219972)
4. [dspice.win.64.0.0.6.exe](https://sourceforge.net/projects/dspice/) dwnload page: <https://sourceforge.net/projects/dspice/>